

Conducting polymer based electrochemical sensor for strontium in nitric acid medium

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A polyaniline/polycarbonate membrane impregnated with a receptor molecule di-*tert*-butylcyclohexano-18C6 (DtBuCH18C6) was employed as an electrochemical sensor for Sr^{II} ion in nitric acid medium. Behavior of the molecular device was studied as a function of variables like oxidation potential, crown ether concentration and nitric acid concentration. The sensor response was linear in the limited Sr^{II} concentration range of 1×10^{-10} to 1×10^{-9} M, beyond which a saturation effect was observed.

Molecular devices based on the electronic switching properties of conducting polymers are well known^{1,2}. Polyaniline (PANI) based electrochemical sensing devices have been reported for the estimation of glucose, urea, and triglycerides and also for the detection of K^I, Ba^{II} and Sr^{III} using 18-crown6 (18C6) adsorbed on PANI/polycarbonate membrane^{2,3}. The device configuration used in the work was gold interdigitated microelectrode pair (IMP) deposited on an oxidized silicon wafer and two closely spaced Pt wires. But this configuration had marked disadvantages, viz. (i) its fabrication was expensive and time consuming and (ii) it required delicate handling during measurements especially with polymer grown on Pt twin wires which could unbridge. In the present studies, PANI grown on gold plated polycarbonate membrane and doped with DtBuCH18C6 was used. DtBuCH18C6 was chosen in view of its favourable cavity size as well as its selective complexation with Sr^{II}. ⁹⁰Sr is a fission product which needs to be monitored in the environmental samples at very low concentration in view of its long radiological as well as biological half-lives. It was thus fascinating to work with an electronic switching device which responds to the trace concentration of Sr^{II} ion on the basis of its binding ability. Its performance has been evaluated as a function of several factors, such as oxidation potential, HNO₃ concentration, crown ether concentration and the loading time.

Results and Discussion

Device configuration for conductance measurement is shown in Fig. 1.

Initial studies were carried out in the range of 10^{-10} to 10^{-3} M of Sr^{II} in 3 M HNO₃. The plot $\Delta g/g_0$ vs log [Sr²⁺]

reached maximum between 10^{-9} and 10^{-8} M and then fell rapidly with higher [Sr^{II}], viz. 10^{-8} to 10^{-3} M (Fig. 2). Thus a switching type of behavior was observed when PANI film

Fig. 1. Device configuration for conductance measurement; $I_1 - I_2 = I_d$ when drain voltage is 20 mV and $I_1 - I_2 = I_0$ when drain voltage is 0 mV.

was loaded with 0.02 M DtBuCH18C6 in 1-butanol. Thereafter, the study was carried out in the range 10^{-10} to 10^{-8} M of Sr^{II}. The ratio $\Delta g/g_0$ increases from 10^{-10} M of Sr^{II} and reaches a maximum at 7×10^{-10} M and is steady thereafter

up to $1 \times 10^{-8} M$. This could be explained by the fact that the crown sites (molecular recognition unit, in polymer matrix, transducer) were occupied first gradually and then completely by Sr^{II} . Thereafter, the response fell sharply which could be due to the degradation of the polymer film as suggested by the fact that the polymer did not regain its previous electroactivity. Thus a non-covalent interaction exists between the molecular recognition unit, DtBuCH18C6 and the transducer, PANI.

Fig. 2. Variation in relative change in conductance ($\Delta g/g_0$) of the polymeric device (Au-PC) loaded with 0.02 M DtBCH18C6 in 1-butanol on exposure to various Sr^{II} concentrations at 3 M HNO_3 ; $V_G = -0.8 V$ vs Pt/PANI.

Effect of nitric acid concentration :

The HNO_3 concentration range investigated in the present study was 0.1–4.0 M. No significant change in response was noticed for varying concentrations of Sr^{II} at either 0.1 or 2 M HNO_3 . At 4 M HNO_3 , the system showed very good response but only in a very narrow range of Sr^{II} concentration. However, the measurement in this medium was not reproducible. Degradation of the film under these conditions was suspected since the colour of the PANI film changed from light blue to dull yellow. At 3 M HNO_3 , the system showed a switching characteristics and the measurements were reproducible. Thus, 3 M HNO_3 appeared to be the most suitable medium for Sr^{II} detection.

Effect of crown ether concentration :

The sensor response $\Delta g/g_0$ vs $\log [Sr^{II}]$, for various concentrations of the crown is shown in Fig. 3. This was attempted to understand the role of crown sites availability for binding Sr^{II} . At higher concentration of the crown, viz. 0.02 M, saturation occurred at $10^{-8} M$ of Sr^{II} , beyond which the response decreased sharply (Fig. 2). PANI film treated with lower concentration of the crown showed linear behavior instead of switching type. The observed response

was found to be linear between 1×10^{-10} and $1 \times 10^{-9} M$ of Sr^{II} for the crown concentration of 0.2 mM. Control experiment was also carried out in the absence of crown. Hence the response was due to the Sr^{II} binding to DtBuCH18C6 present in the bulk PANI.

Fig. 3. Effect of various concentrations of crown loaded device on its response on exposure to various Sr^{II} concentrations in 3 M HNO_3 ; $V_G = -0.8 V$ vs Pt/PANI.

Effect of time on crown ether loading :

The effect of variation in time of loading of crown (0.02 M) on Au-PC/PANI film was studied in the range 3–20 min. As the time of loading increased initially, the amount of crown ether that went into the film too increased, thereby improving the sensitivity of the sensor. Such behavior was observed only when loading time increased from 3 to 6 min. On further increase of loading time to 10 min, the conductance decreased but the nature of the curve did not change. But for loading time of 15 and 20 min, not only did the response of the electrode deteriorate but also the nature of curve changed significantly. Plateau region clearly seen for loading time upto 10 min disappeared for the longer loading periods. It appears that the transduction ability of PANI film deteriorated on longer exposure. The optimum loading time of 6 min was used in the present studies.

Effect of oxidation potential :

It was thought of interest to study the influence of over oxidizing PANI film at 100 mV more (anodic) than the usual potential limit by cycling 2, 5 and 10 times at 3 M HNO_3 before measurements in order to achieve the linear response in a broader concentration range of Sr^{II} . The change in conductivity before growing PANI and after growing PANI was found to be 1.3, 1.0 and 0.6 order of magnitude, respectively. Then crown was loaded from 0.02 M solution. It was observed that irrespective of the number of cycles, the increasing response was found upto 4×10^{-10}

M of Sr^{II} , beyond which response decreased. The decreased response could be due to the presence of lesser amount of electroactive polymer in the over oxidized film.

Reproducibility of Sr^{II} measurement :

The Au-PC/PANI film treated with 10^{-4} M DtBuCH18C6 was used for repeated measurement of 2×10^{-10} and 7×10^{-10} M of Sr^{II} in 3 M HNO_3 in order to examine the reproducibility of the sensor. Each measurement was preceded by rinsing the sensor with 3 M HNO_3 solution. The results showed that the sensor response was reproducible with a relative standard deviation (RSD) of $\pm 6.1\%$ (15 determinations) and $\pm 5.8\%$ (8 determinations) for 2×10^{-10} and 7×10^{-10} M of Sr^{II} , respectively.

Electrochemical determination of Sr^{II} in a synthetic mixture :

High level waste (HLW) comprises principally of alpha emitting actinide isotopes like ^{239}Pu , ^{241}Am , ^{243}Am , ^{245}Cm , ^{237}Np and beta emitting isotopes like ^{93}Zr , ^{90}Sr , ^{137}Cs , ^{126}Sn , ^{99}Tc and ^{135}Cs apart from several activation products like ^{59}Ni , ^{63}Ni and ^{94}Nb . However, ^{90}Sr and ^{137}Cs are the major contributors towards radioactivity in the HLW stored for a few years. Radiometric determination of ^{90}Sr in HLW is cumbersome in view of the presence of large number of beta emitters. An attempt was made to explore the possibility of employing the molecular device developed in the present work for the electrochemical determination of Sr^{II} in 3 M HNO_3 . Relative conductance of possible interfering metal ions like Ba^{II} and Nd^{III} was also measured.

Initial study conducted in a wide concentration range, 10^{-8} to 10^{-3} M of Ba^{II} and 10^{-5} to 10^{-3} M of Nd^{III} /3 M HNO_3 with 0.02 M crown treated Au-PC/PANI film showed that the maximum response was in 10^{-7} to 10^{-5} M for Ba^{II} and 10^{-4} to 10^{-3} M for Nd^{III} . There was negligible response of Ba^{II} and Nd^{III} in the concentration range of 10^{-10} to 10^{-9} M where Sr^{II} showed maximum response.

A suitable mixture containing 5×10^{-10} M Sr^{II} , 5×10^{-10} M Ba^{II} and 1×10^{-9} M Nd^{III} (ratio of the metal ions was similar to the composition of pressurized heavy water reactor (PHWR) high level waste solution) was taken to measure the response of the electrochemical system described earlier. The relative change in conductivity of the developed electrochemical sensor was found to correspond to the expected Sr^{II} concentration within $\pm 10\%$.

Conclusion :

Possibility of determining Sr^{II} in the presence of Ba^{II} and Nd^{III} has been demonstrated using a molecular device based on PANI/DtBuCH18C6. Limited linear range is, however, a disadvantage of this method. It is obvious that an unknown sample need to be diluted till one finds the relative conductance in the expected range of Sr^{II} solution

of 10^{-10} to 10^{-9} . One can correlate the concentration obtained from the calibration graph with the unknown concentration by using the exact dilution factor.

Experimental

Aniline (E. Merck) distilled under nitrogen atmosphere was used for preparing monomer solution. Di-*t*-butylcyclohexano-18-crown-6 (Eichrom Industries), $BaCO_3$ (E. Merck, G.R.) and $SrCO_3$ (specpure) were used as such. A stock solution of 0.02 M DtBuCH18C6 was prepared in 1-butanol and dilute solutions were prepared from this stock solution. Water from Millipore ultrapurification system was used throughout. Polycarbonate (PC) membranes (10 μ thickness and 1.2 μ pore dia) produced by 'track etch' method were obtained from Millipore Corporation.

EG & G 362 scanning potentiostat (for the preparation of the reference electrode), Pine AFRDE bipotentiostat (for cyclic voltammogram and *in situ* resistance measurements) connected independently to Linseis XYt recorder were used.

Working electrode : The masks were made by cutting equidistant stripes of 3 mm width at a distance of 0.85 mm on an aluminium sheet for gold coating (thickness 0.1 μ m) employing an indigenously made vacuum evaporation system. This way gold strips of 3 mm width were obtained on the PC membrane by placing the mask on each side of the membrane successively. Gold coated strips (1 cm long) were used as electrode. The strip was held in a plastic clip holder containing thin Pt tips on both sides for contact. The gold strips on either side acted as electrodes during polymerization and subsequently as the 'source' and 'drain' during conductivity measurements (Fig. 1).

Electrode assembly : Gold strip (PC membrane coated with moderately thick film of PANI), Pt foil and Pt coated with PANI (Pt/PANI) were used as working, counter and reference electrodes, respectively. The latter was prepared fresh before each experiment. Its potential was found to be +0.6 V vs SCE in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 . The resistance across unbridged gold strip electrode used in this study was >200 M Ω .

Electrochemical polymerization of PANI (preparation of working electrode) : Prior to growing PANI on to the working electrode, its surface was cleaned by cycling five times between -2.0 to +1.6 V vs SCE across the gold strip immersed in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 and if the CV showed the characteristic peaks of gold then it was used for growing PANI film. PANI was grown onto the gold strip and into the pores of the membrane by electropolymerization of a monomer solution of 0.1 M aniline in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 by potentiodynamic cycling between -0.2 to +0.8 V vs SCE for 25 min. A moderately thick film of PANI was formed on both sides of the membrane as well as on the walls of the pores inside the PC membrane since the polycationic

species of PANI is completely insoluble in 0.5 M H₂SO₄. The PANI coated membrane, Au-PC/PANI thus obtained was used for measurements.

Reference electrode : The Pt wire (0.5 mm thick) was cleaned using chromic/sulfuric acid mixture, followed by electrochemical cleaning in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ for 15 min. CV was recorded to check the surface of Pt by cycling between -0.2 and +1.2 V vs SCE in 0.5 M H₂SO₄. When characteristic CV peaks for Pt surface were obtained, PANI was grown electrochemically (by cycling between -0.2 and +0.8 V vs SCE at a sweep rate of 50 mV s⁻¹ in 0.1 M aniline monomer solution) in 0.5 M H₂SO₄. It was rinsed with MilliQ water to free it from traces of aniline, held at -0.2 V vs SCE in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ for 5 min and stored in MilliQ water before use.

Resistance measurement : A schematic representation of the set-up for *in situ* resistance measurement is shown in Fig. 1. A fixed potential was applied on the working electrode and the current was measured. The gate voltage (V_G) from -0.8 to -0.4 V vs reference electrode was applied for various concentrations of HNO₃. A difference of 20 mV was kept as the drain voltage (V_D). The current obtained is designated as I_d . Then the drain voltage was kept at 0 mV and the current obtained is designated as I_0 . Direct determination ($I_d - I_0$) was carried out in one step for each value of V_G . The resistance was measured by the formula,

$$R = \frac{V_D}{I_d - I_0}$$

The conductance was measured in 0.1, 2, 3 and 4 M nitric acid. DtBuCH18C6 (of a particular concentration ranging

from 0.2 to 20 mM in *n*-butanol) was adsorbed into the PANI matrix by physisorption. Conductance was measured both before and after loading crown. The crown loaded film was exposed thereafter to the analyte solution of Sr^{II} (Ba^{II}, Nd^{III}). The sensor 'response' is represented by relative change in conductance, $\Delta g/g_0$, where g_0 is the conductance of the sensor in the supporting electrolyte in the absence of analyte and $\Delta g = g - g_0$ (where g is the conductance of the sensor in the presence of analyte). The ratio, $\Delta g/g_0$, normalizes the sensor response and minimizes variations from sensor to sensor.

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